

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D5.4 Piping, Auxiliary Equipment and Cables Connections

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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermozone tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
ORC	'Orcan Energy AG' or 'Organic Rankine Cycle'
PU	Public
RHX	Recovery Heat Exchanger
TC	Thermocouple
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

Figure 2: Plans of construction - views of components (top) and piping (bottom)

1.4 TIME-TABLE OF THE CONSTRUCTION

The construction of the piping and auxiliary equipment was executed from January 2022 to August 2022. The main steps of the construction are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Main steps of the construction of the piping and auxiliary equipment

Date	Action	Participants
24-28/01/2022	Beginning of manufacturing of piping	CNRS
31/01-04/02/2022	-Implementation of pumps in the circuits. -Starting of construction of the combustor by AALBORG in Spain.	CNRS AALBORG
07-18/02/2022	-Implementation of all piping in the container, and small expansion vessel on the roof of the container. -Construction of the supporting structure for the container at Themis site -Integration of the burner in the combustor	CNRS AALBORG
21/02-04/03/2022	-The container with the piping is finished -The combustor is finished	CNRS AALBORG
07-11/03/2022	Installation of the combustor on the roof of the container. Installation of the shelter.	CNRS
21/03/2022	Delivery and installation of the components at Themis site	CNRS
22/03-01/04/2022	Construction of the outdoor piping Implementation of the auxiliary equipment	CNRS
11/04/2022	Delivery of thermal oil at Themis site	CNRS
22/04/2022	The control cabinet is installed in the container	CNRS
18/07-03/08/2022	Thermal insulation of the piping	CNRS

1.5 PICTURES OF THE CONSTRUCTION

Container – Oil circuits

RHX in container

Container - Air circuit

Container – Top – supporting structure

Oil tank

Oil tank – Outer envelope

Oil tank – top cover

Instruments & parts

Figure 3: Beginning of the construction of piping [24-28 Jan 2022]

Figure 4: Implementation of pumps in the circuit [31 Jan – 04 Feb 2022]

Figure 5: Supporting structure at Themis site [31 Jan – 04 Feb 2022]

Figure 6: Combustor under construction, by Aalborg CSP [31 Jan – 04 Feb 2022]

Figure 7: Implementation of all piping in the container (left), and small expansion vessel on the roof of the container (right) [07-18 Feb 2022]

Figure 8: Integration of the burner in the combustor [07-18 Feb 2022]

Figure 9: The container with the piping [21 Feb-04 Mar 2022]

Figure 10: The combustor is manufactured [21 Feb - 04 Mar 2022]

Figure 11: Installation of the combustor on the roof of the container [07-11 Mar 2022]

Figure 12: Installation of the shelter [07-11 Mar 2022]

Installation of the container at Themis site

Installation of the oil tank at Themis site

Installation of the combustor and shelter at Themis site

Installation of the ORC group at Themis site

Figure 13: Delivery and installation of the components at Themis site [21 Mar 2022]

Figure 14: Components installed at Themis site – Views from S (top) and from N (bottom)[21 Mar 2022]

Figure 15: Construction of the outdoor piping and implementation of the auxiliary equipment [22 Mar -01 Apr 2022]

Figure 16: The control cabinet is installed in the container [22 Apr2022]

Figure 17: Thermal insulation of the piping [18 Jul – 03 Aug 2022]

2. SITUATION ON 31 AUGUST 2022

The Grant Agreement of POLYPHEM ends on 31 August 2022. At this date, the piping and the auxiliary equipment are installed at Themis site. The cables are connected. The actuators are powered.